

USEFUL AND HARMFUL ASPECTS OF COTTONSEED OIL

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ABSTRACT

Cottonseed oil is an oil obtained by pressing the seed or extracting it with solvents. Pure cottonseed oil dissolves well in most organic solvents. It is a light yellow transparent liquid and belongs to the group of semi-drying oils. This article describes cottonseed oil, its beneficial and harmful properties.

Keywords: Cottonseed oil, extraction, natural oil, hydrogenated oil, phytosterols, fatty acids.

There are several types of vegetable oil: sunflower, corn, olive, cotton, etc. Cottonseed oil is obtained by processing cottonseed. This plant belongs to the Malvaceae family. Cottonseed oil comes in a variety of colors. Color from dark to light. It depends on how the oil is refined and further processed. Unrefined cottonseed oil is used to make drying oil. Refined oil is used for cooking purposes. It is even used to make margarine.

Useful properties of cottonseed oil: The chemical composition of cottonseed oil includes tocopherols, phytosterols, as well as palmitic, oleic, stearic,

arachidonic and linoleic acids. But the oil may contain other components. It all depends on the type of plant from which the oil is produced. Due to the composition of these substances, it is also used for medicinal purposes. Cottonseed oil prevents the deposition of cholesterol on the walls of blood vessels. This is because this product has the ability to reduce the absorption of cholesterol by the intestinal walls. Among the benefits of oil, its use in food leads to the strengthening and strengthening of the immune system. In addition, it has wound-healing, anti-inflammatory and antihistamine effects. In addition, it can be used as a medicine for the treatment of diabetes mellitus, allergic and dermatological diseases. Useful substances contained in this product participate in the formation of bone tissue. It can also be used to relieve skin burns. Gossypol, which is part of the oil, prevents the spread of viruses in the blood. Cottonseed oil can replace walnut oil. This is a solution for people who have an allergic reaction to peanut butter. It has a positive effect on the nervous system, it calms it down. A small amount of oil is recommended for people with peptic ulcers. Cottonseed oil is also used in cosmetology. This is a component added to masks and face creams. Oil helps to get rid of dry skin. Funds based on it help to keep the skin young. It also increases the protective functions of the skin. Cottonseed oil is also good for hair. It gives them a healthy look, shine and silkiness. Soap is made from it. Cottonseed oil is the base of this soap. It has a positive effect on the condition of the skin of the hands.

Harmful properties of cottonseed oil: Contraindication to the use of oil is the presence of individual intolerance to any component that is part of it. Also, it should always be noted that refined oil is beneficial. Its excessive use for medicinal purposes can cause reproductive system disorders. Almost all vegetable oils are beneficial for human health. Some of them, like olive oil, have an impressive list of medicinal properties. But not all healthy fats are known to the general public. Cottonseed oil, which is very popular in the West, is hardly used in

Russia.

It is important to use only refined oil, which contains:

1. **Fatty acids** - the oil has a high content of oleic, linseed oil and other oils;
2. **Vitamins** - the product is especially rich in B, A and E vitamins;
3. **Phytosterols** - regulate cholesterol levels;
4. **Polyunsaturated acids** - include linoleic acid, which is not produced by

the body.

The oil improves hair growth, eases hair breakage and stimulates blood circulation. It is taken to prepare therapeutic masks to restore especially damaged hair after chemical or dyeing. The product has bactericidal properties. Improves the condition of the skin, relieves itching of the lips, protects against cracking and frostbite. It is often used for massage and can be used to treat baby's skin to prevent sebaceous glands rashes. The peculiarity of cotton compress is that it effectively fights against high cholesterol. Fat prevents the absorption of harmful substances by intestinal walls, as a result of which the risk of developing atherosclerosis decreases. Refined fat is similar to sunflower and olive oil. It has an unrefined reddish color. In cooking, only refined oil is used, from which the harmful substance, gossypol, is removed. In large quantities, it poisons the body and disrupts reproductive functions. Do not add unrefined oil to food.... Also, it is not even used for cosmetic purposes, although crude oil makes good soap with beneficial properties. Refined oil is practically harmless. Only those who suffer from individual intolerance cannot consume it. Many people do not like the taste of cotton. It is quite possible to replace it with peanuts or corn. Cottonseed oil is very popular in cosmetology due to its rich composition and light texture. This natural product is used for all types of hair, but its effect is especially noticeable on dry, damaged hair. To strengthen the roots, it is used in massage mixtures and shampoos, it can be enriched with sprays, balms and conditioners for shine and strength. In its pure form, it is useful to use it for the care of the ends, apply a few

drops to the pads of the fingers and spread it with light movements on the damaged areas.

COMPOSITION OF COTTON OIL:

The chemical composition of cottonseed oil, as well as the quality of the oil, depends on the place and type of cotton.

- **MYRISTIC COATING** - ensures better penetration of the components used for cosmetic purposes into the skin;
- **LINOLEIC ACID** - vitamin F, helps maintain the hydro balance of the skin, UF is a filter;
- **PALMITOLEIC ACID** - actively supports the renewal of mature skin;
- **STEAR ACID** - helps to restore the protective function of the skin;
- **PALMITIC ACID** - improves synthesis of collagen, hyaluronate;
- **ARACHINIC ACID** - has an anti-inflammatory effect;
- **OLEIC ACID**- activates lipid metabolism.
- **POLYUNSATURATED ACIDS** - includes LINOLEIC ACID, which is not produced by the body;
- **FATTY ACIDS** - cottonseed oil contains a lot of OLEIC, linseed oil and other oils;
- **VITAMINS** - the product is especially rich in B, A and E vitamins;
- **PHYTOSTEROLS** - regulate cholesterol levels;

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